

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of time of herbicide application on crop damage and weed control in wet-seeded rice

M. O. Mabbayad and K. Moody,
Agronomy Department, IRRI

Wet seeding rice (sowing pregerminated seed on puddled soil) is increasing in importance in several Southeast Asian countries. When herbicides are used for weed control in this type of rice culture, selectivity is often marginal because the rice and the weeds are at the same development stage. Herbicide selectivity may be improved by varying application time.

To determine the effect of time of herbicide application on weed control and crop damage in wet-seeded rice, residual herbicides were applied 3 d before seeding (DBS) and 0, 3, and 6 d after seeding (DAS), and propanil, a contact herbicide, was applied 6, 9, and 12 DAS. The field was saturated when the herbicides were applied 3 DBS and 0 and 3 DAS. Water depth was 3-4 cm when the herbicides were applied 6 DAS. Hand weeded (25 and 40 DAS) and unweeded checks were included for comparison.

Pregerminated IR36 seeds were broadcast at 100 kg/ha on 22 Aug 1983. Crop stand counts were determined 30 DAS and weed weights 45 DAS from two 0.5- × 0.5-m quadrats per plot.

Significant stand reductions occurred when thiobencarb and piperophos - 2,4-D were applied 0 and 3 DAS and when butachlor - 2,4-D were applied 0, 3, and 6 DAS (see table). No standard reduction was observed with other herbicides.

Eleven weed species occurred in the experimental area. The major ones, in order of decreasing importance, were *Paspalum distichum*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Sphenoclea zeylanica*, *Echinochloa glabrescens*, and *Cyperus difformis*.

None of the herbicides controlled weeds as well as the hand-weeded

Effect of time of herbicide application on crop stand and weed weight, IRRI, 1983 wet season.

Herbicide and rate (kg ai/ha)	Time of application	Crop stand count (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^a (g/m ²)
Pretilachlor safener (0.5)	+3 DBS	287 a	19 hi
	0 DAS	255 abc	21 ghi
	3 DAS	280 ab	47 c-i
	6 DAS	229 abc	82 a-i
Pretilachlor + safener (0.75)	3 DBS	211 a-d	45 c-i
	0 DAS	221 a-d	44 c-i
	3 DAS	247 abc	33 e-i
	6 DAS	279 ab	30 f-i
Butachlor (0.5)	3 DBS	193 a-f	39 d-i
	0 DAS	207 a-d	53 b-i
	3 DAS	257 abc	26 ghi
	6 DAS	250 abc	121 a-g
Butachlor (0.75)	3 DBS	233 abc	16 i
	0 DAS	287 a	33 e-i
	3 DAS	256 abc	100 a-h
	6 DAS	199 a-e	102 a-h
Thiobencarb (1.5)	3 DBS	220 a-d	44 c-i
	0 DAS	167 c-d	139 a-g
	3 DAS	101 gh	107 a-g
	6 DAS	239 abc	66 a-i
Butachlor-2,4-D (0.45-0.30)	3 DBS	235 abc	46 c-i
	0 DAS	108 fgh	101 a-h
	3 DAS	129 d-h	103 a-h
	6 DAS	184 b-g	180 a-d
Piperophos-2,4-D (0.33-0.17)	3 DBS	220 a-d	69 a-i
	0 DAS	115 e-h	222 abc
	3 DAS	90 h	176 a-e
	6 DAS	226 abc	51 a-i
DPX 5384 (0.5)	3 DBS	288 a	68 a-i
	0 DAS	247 abc	70 a-i
	3 DAS	205 a-d	36 d-i
	6 DAS	281 ab	52 c-i
Propanil (2.5)	6 DAS	241 abc	156 a-f
	9 DAS	239 abc	277 ab
	12 DAS	220 a-d	78 a-i
Hand weeded	25 + 40 DAS	259 abc	3 j
Not weeded	-	207 a-d	281 a

^a Backtransformed means of the transformed means. In a column means followed by common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

check (see table). Application 3 DBS of all the residual herbicides except DPX 5384 and piperophos - 2,4-D significantly reduced weed weight compared to the untreated check. When herbicides were applied 6 DAS, pretilachlor + safener at 0.75 kg/ha and DPX 5384 were superior to the untreated check. Propanil controlled weeds poorly at all application times.

When averaged across residual herbicide treatments, weed weights were significantly lower when the herbicides

were applied 3 DBS than at the other times (50 g/m² vs an average of 111 g/m²). When averaged across application times, pretilachlor + safener and butachlor were superior to piperophos-2,4-D in controlling weeds while pretilachlor + safener were superior to butachlor - 2,4-D.

Results indicate that for crop safety and superior weed control in wet-seeded rice, residual herbicides should be applied before seeding.